

**Shadow Report to the
Sixth Report Submitted by Romania
to the Secretary General of the Council of Europe
on the Implementation of
the Framework Convention for the Protection of
National Minorities**

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1. Introduction

The report is submitted by the Bálványos Institute, a think tank based in Cluj-Napoca/Kolozsvár conducting social and public policy research on topics concerning the Hungarian community in Transylvania. The Institute, publishes research reports, sociological studies and public policy analyses, based on empirical research and analysis, directed at decision makers, NGOs and civil advocacy groups.

This report focuses on the implementation of the FCNM concerning three issues: 1) the use of Hungarian language in administration, 2) transparency of in state funding system for minorities, and 3) regression in social security rights of Roma children. In each section, we conclude with a set of recommendations on how the ACFC should encourage Romania to meet its commitments under the FCNM in relation to minority rights, the Hungarian minority and the Hungarian speaking Roma community.

The report was prepared by two experts, Tibor Toró and Tamás Kiss, based on the results of extensive empirical research based on the results of extensive empirical research focusing on Hungarian language education and the use of Hungarian language in relation with administrative and local authorities.

2. The use of Hungarian language in dealing with local public authorities and use of place names in Hungarian language (FCNM Articles 10, 11)

The first part of our report focuses on Hungarian language use in dealings with local authorities, use of bilingual/multilingual place signs and the availability of widely used administrative texts and forms in bilingual versions. It should be noted that in 2019 a new version of the Administrative Code (GEO no. 57/2019), which replaced the 2015/2001 Law on Local Public Administration. Provisions regarding minority language use in public administration were included in the new Administrative Code, allowing speakers of minority languages to use their mother tongue in relation with administrative and local authorities if the percentage of the majority was above 20 percent in the given administrative unit.

The Administrative Code stipulates the following rights:

- the possibility for oral and written communication in the minority language with local authorities and deconcentrated public services (Article; 94 (1), 195 (1))
- the publication of bilingual forms and widely used administrative text both in the minority language and Romanian (Article 195 (2))
- the obligation of local authorities to publish the agenda of council meetings (Article 135 (5)), and administrative documents with a normative character, such as council decisions (Article 198 (3)) bilingually
- the use of the minority language at local council meetings (Article 138 (3))
- The employment of public-facing staff capable of speaking the minority language (Article 195(5));
- The use of bilingual place names (Article 195(6))

In addition, Article 12 of the Rules for Implementing the Provisions of Law no. 544/2001 on free access to public information (GD no. 123/2002) stipulates that in administrative units where the proportion

of a national minority is above 20%, information communicated ex officio need to be published both in Romanian and the language of the respective minority.

In the following paragraphs, we argue that when adopting the new Administrative Code Romanian legislators employed an unreasonably high threshold for minority language use. Moreover, we demonstrate that this legislative act constitutes a step back in minority language use in dealings with administrative and local authorities. We also provide information on implementation, namely on the extent to which Hungarian can be effectively used in written and oral communication with local authorities.

1.1. Unreasonably high threshold and the lack of an alternative numeric threshold

The previous version of the Administrative Code (Law no. 215/2001) defined a statutory threshold of 20 percent for the applicability of minority language rights in dealings with local authorities. The newly adopted law did not change this threshold (see Art. 94 (1) of GEO no. 57/2019), but introduced Art. 94 (2)¹ that allows local authorities where the number of the minority does not reach 20 percent to ensure the use of the language of national minorities in the administrative-territorial unit in their own competence. It is important to emphasize that local authorities could opt for introducing language related regulations even before the new legislation was introduced, so the provisions cannot be considered a lowering of the threshold as they are not mandatory for these administrative units.

In order to implement this, it might be necessary to adopt a flexible and context-specific approach in defining the threshold, which would be a solution for large urban centres, where despite their high number, the proportion of Hungarians is below the threshold. The most stunning example is the case of Cluj-Napoca/Kolozsvár, where approximately 33 000 Hungarians live without the right to use their mother tongue in their interactions with the administrative and local authorities.

Alternative numerical threshold (e.g., 5000 persons) has been proposed by the Democratic Alliance of Hungarians in Romania (RMDSZ) to the Romanian parliament without success. GEO no. 57/2019 did not lower the threshold or offer an alternative numerical threshold.

1.2. A major step back in use minority language in dealing with administrative and local authorities

Article 131 of the repealed Law no. 215/2001 guaranteed minority language use in dealing with administrative and local authorities even in cases when the percentage of a minority dropped below the 20 percent threshold after the date of entry into force of the law. The newly adopted GEO no. 57/2019, however, no longer stipulates the maintenance of this important and welcomed status quo related to language rights.

According to Article 131 of Law no. 215/2001, the 20 percent threshold was calculated based on 1992 census figures. Thus, minorities enjoyed certain language rights even if they were affected by negative

¹ Art. 94 par. 2: *“The local public administration authorities provided in par. (1), by decision, may decide to ensure the use of the language of national minorities in the administrative-territorial units in which the citizens belonging to the national minorities do not reach the threshold provided in par. (1).”*

demographic changes. Art. 94 (1)² and Art. 604 (1)³ of GEO no. 57/2019, on the other hand, removed this guarantee to maintain the status quo as it existed to the most favorable census 'results, and stipulate updating the conditions of minority language use with each census. This change in regulation has several consequences. This deprives a significant number of Hungarians from using their language in dealing with administrative and local authorities (see **Table 2** in the Annex for a detailed list of municipalities. In cases where the previous law had not been implemented properly beforehand, GEO no. 57/2019 practically makes local authorities unaccountable for the lack of bilingual signs, for their failures of implementations. The most important example is that of the growing municipality of Cluj-Napoca/Kolozsvár, which is the cultural center of the Hungarian community in Romania and a city traditionally inhabited in substantial numbers by ethnic Hungarians. Today the city is home of 33 000 Hungarians. They constituted more than 20 percent of the total population in 1992, but their proportion has fallen below this threshold afterwards.

1.3. Defections in law implementation

In this respect we rely on data collected in 2023, during which we assessed 323 municipalities where these legal provisions are binding for Hungarian language. Data was gathered triangulating three methods: 1) structured on-site observation, 2) experimental telephone inquiries, and 3) the analysis of local government websites and official Facebook pages. The results were compared with previous baseline studies, specifically the 2008 survey by the Romanian Institute for Research on National Minorities (ISPMN) and the 2014 survey by the Bálványos Institute.

We identified five dimensions of minority language use in dealings with local authorities:

- 1) *bilingual signage* – they represent the most basic level of language use. They require minimal intervention of local authorities and serve a primarily symbolic rather than functional purpose
- 2) *oral communication* – it represents the next level, which is vital for minority language use in daily administrative procedures. However, without written language use, minority language practice remains at the level of informality.
- 3) *written communication* – elevates the status of the minority language, yet more symmetric language use is only achieved through the translation of official documents and the introduction of bilingual forms
- 4) *the translation of official documents* and 5) *the availability of bilingual forms* – the distinction between these two is significant: while publishing official documents in the minority language facilitates only one-way communication, providing bilingual forms enables citizens to actively engage with the administration in their mother tongue.

² Art. 94, par. 1: “*In the administrative-territorial units/subdivisions in which the citizens belonging to a national minority have a share of over 20% of the population, established at the last census, the local public administration authorities, the public institutions subordinated to them, as well as the public services deconcentrated ensure the use, in their relations with them, also of the language of the respective national minority, in accordance with the provisions of the Constitution, of this code and of the international treaties to which Romania is a party.*”

³ Art. 604, par. 1: “*The provisions of art. 94, art. 135 para. (5), art. 138 para. (3), art. 195 para. (2) - (6), art. 198 para. (3) and of art. 199 para. (3) are also applicable if, for various reasons, after the entry into force of this code, the share of citizens belonging to a national minority falls below the percentage provided in art. 94, until the date of validation of the results of the next census.*”

1.3.1. Bilingual signage and topographical indications

Most municipalities have installed bilingual place name signs; however, the current data reveals a slight regression compared to the 2008 baseline (**Figure 1**). This suggests that during the routine maintenance or replacement of place name signs, some of the local authorities did not ensure the installation of bilingual signs. In municipalities where Hungarians have the majority in the local council, compliance remains high, with 92% mounting bilingual place name signs.

Figure 1. Are there any bilingual signs at the entrances and exits of the settlement?

Regarding the inscriptions at the façade of administrative buildings, the proportion of municipalities displaying bilingual signs at the facade of Mayor's Offices has increased since 2008 (from 82% to 91%). A marginal improvement was also observed for post offices (from 29% to 31%). Conversely, bilingual signage on police stations demonstrates a downward trend, declining from 14% to 10% (**Figure 2**). Notably, for police stations, the ethnic and political composition of the municipality has almost no impact on language display: the proportion of police stations with bilingual signage is below 15% even in municipalities with Hungarian majority too.

Figure 2. Are there any bilingual signs on the façade of the following institutions?

1.3.2. Oral communication in dealing with local authorities

For oral communication in minority languages to be effectively realized in public administration, two conditions must be met simultaneously: municipal employees must possess the necessary language skills, and the authorities must proactively encourage the use of the minority language.

Based on the structured observation carried out in the framework of our research, in 62% of the mayor's offices Hungarian language could be used orally in all departments. This proportion was of 87% in Hungarian majority municipalities (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3. Can Hungarian language be used in dealing with the Mayor's Office?

The possibility of oral communication in Hungarian is significantly lower in case of post offices and police stations. Clients can handle administrative matters in Hungarian at post offices in 56% of the surveyed municipalities, whereas for the police, this proportion drops drastically to 14% (**Figure 4**).

Figure 4. Can Hungarian language be used in dealing with the following institutions?

We obtained further data regarding the possibility of language use dealing with local authorities through an experimental telephone survey. In 88% of cases, our operators managed successfully administrative inquiries in Hungarian over the phone. In 71% of the municipalities, the customer service representative answering the call was able to speak Hungarian, while in 17% of cases, the initial respondent, despite lacking language proficiency, successfully transferred the operator to a Hungarian-speaking colleague. In Hungarian-majority municipalities, the success rate reached 94% (Figure 5).

Figure 5. In what language the telephone conversation with the contact person take place?

Nevertheless, despite the significant proportion of Mayor’s Offices able to provide Hungarian-language services, only slightly more than half encouraged actively the use of Hungarian language during the phone calls. In standard administrative interactions, the language of communication is generally determined by the language used to initiate the conversation. If employees of local authorities do offer not proactively the option to use the Hungarian language, citizens rarely request this.

Figure 6. In what language did the contact person answer and introduce her/himself?

Our experimental research indicates that 53% of the Mayors Offices answered the call bilingually or in Hungarian (**Figure 6**). Thus, although in 88% of the offices theoretically it was possible to use the Hungarian language, this possibility has become a reality only if the operators insisted explicitly on it. in Hungarian-majority municipalities 79% of the Mayor’s Offices encouraged and initiated oral communication in Hungarian. Best practices were also identified during our experimental research: in several cases, phone calls were routed to a bilingual automated menu (IVR system) where the client could select his or her preferred language. Widespread adoption of this system would be an excellent solution to encourage proactively minority language use.

A final aspect of oral language use concerns the language of local council meetings. This issue does not affect the access to public services but it is an important indicator of the status of the Hungarian language and it also shows the attitudes of Hungarian councilors regarding minority language use. Data from structured observations reveal that the right to use Hungarian is exercised almost exclusively in municipalities where all local council members speak Hungarian (and in most cases they belong to Hungarian ethnic parties). Official interpretation is provided by a mere 1% of municipal offices (2% in Hungarian-majority councils), while 6% of municipal offices (7% in Hungarian-majority councils) reported relying on ad-hoc interpretation (**Figure 7**).

Figure 7. What is the language spoken by Hungarian councilors at local council meetings?

1.3.3. Written communication in dealing with local authorities

The capacity of local public authorities for written communication in the minority language was assessed based on the languages used on their official websites and official Facebook pages. Additionally, we examined the language used by mayors in their communication on Facebook. To assess trends over time, we compared these findings with a dataset from 2014, utilizing the exact same indicators to ensure comparability.

Regarding official websites, bilingualism has declined since 2014. While 43% of municipal websites were exclusively in Romanian in 2014, this figure rose to 52% in 2023. Meanwhile, the proportion of bilingual websites decreased from 27% to 23% (**Figure 8**). Notably, this decline is primarily attributed to municipalities with Hungarian leadership: in these municipalities, the proportion of exclusively Romanian websites increased from 21% to 29%, while the proportion of those maintaining bilingual websites dropped from 45% to 37%.

Figure 8. What is the language of the official homepage of the Mayor's office?

Conversely, bilingual communication is significantly more robust on social media. Half of all surveyed municipal offices utilize bilingual communication on Facebook (representing two-thirds of the municipalities that maintain a Facebook page) (**Figure 9**). For municipal administrations with Hungarian leadership, this proportion reaches 75%, constituting 96% of those with an active Facebook presence.

Figure 9. What language are the following pages if the mayor and the mayor's office?

In conclusion, while written communication in Hungarian remains generally important to Hungarian-led municipal authorities, there is a visible lack of effort to institutionalize this practice at a formal, official level. While maintaining a Facebook presence undoubtedly facilitates public engagement with residents, a Facebook page does not constitute an official administrative channel. Consequently, this practice barely transcends the level of oral communication, effectively marginalizing the use of the Hungarian language by relegating it to informal spheres.

1.3.4. Translation of official documents

According to the Administrative Code (GEO no. 57/2019, Article 195/2) the translation of official documents and bilingual forms is mandatory in municipalities where the proportion of minorities is above the 20% threshold. In spite of this legislative change (compared to

Unfortunately, a significant regression can be observed across all three document categories compared to the situation in 2008. In 2008, 81% of municipalities translated public announcements, 52% published their council meeting agendas in Hungarian, and 38% made council resolutions available in the minority language to the public. By 2023, these compliance rates had declined to 39%, 22% and 15%. Unfortunately, these numbers are rather low in the case of Hungarian-majority municipalities as well, 56%, 33%, and 22%, respectively (**Figure 10**).

Figure 10. In what language are the following documents published on the noticeboard of the Mayor's office?

In light of these findings, it is evident that the translation of official documents, a fundamental pillar of formal minority language use, is scarcely implemented by local councils. Regrettably, municipalities with a Hungarian majority do not constitute an exception to this widespread lack of compliance.

1.3.5. Bilingual forms

One of the significant achievements of the Administrative Code introduced in 2019 was that it introduced the obligation of local public authorities to provide bilingual forms to the public. This was an important legislative advancement, especially considering that in 2008, 33% of municipal offices (and 46% of Hungarian-majority councils) provided these forms voluntarily, even when it was not legally mandated.

Despite this improved legislative framework, most local authorities no longer utilize this practice. We found bilingual standardized forms in only 5% of the surveyed municipal offices. Regrettably, municipalities with Hungarian leadership perform only marginally better in this regard, with a compliance rate of just 8% (**Figure 11**).

Figure 11. In what language are the standardized official forms provided by local councils on the spot and online?

1.3.6. The status of Hungarian language in local administration: a summary

Based on the dimensions presented above, we can map the current state of Hungarian language use in dealing with local authorities. The table below outlines the indicators used to assess each dimension:

Table 1. Hungarian language use in dealing with local authorities

Dimension	Indicators
Bilingual signs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are there bilingual topographical settlement signs? - Are there bilingual signs on the facade of the Mayor's Office?
Oral communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can citizens access services in Hungarian across all departments of the Mayor's Office? - Does the municipal office actively encourage minority language use (e.g., answering phone calls bilingually or in Hungarian without knowing the caller's mother tongue in advance)?
Written communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is the official website of the municipal administration bilingual? - Is the official Facebook page of the municipal administration bilingual? - Is the mayor's professional Facebook page bilingual?
Translation of official documents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is the agenda for local council meetings available in Hungarian on the public notice board? - Are normative council resolutions available in Hungarian on the public notice board? - Are the municipal office's notices of public interest available in Hungarian on the public notice board?
Bilingual forms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the municipal office provide any bilingual standardized administrative forms for citizens accessing public services?

Linguistic rights were considered fully implemented within a specific dimension only if all the listed criteria for that category were met. For instance, a municipality was deemed compliant regarding **Bilingual signage** only if all settlement entry and exit signs were bilingual *and* there was a bilingual

sign on the facade of the municipal building. Similarly, **Oral communication** was considered fulfilled if administration in Hungarian was possible *and* the authority actively encouraged it by answering phone calls in the minority language. **Written Communication** required the authority to use bilingual communication across all its official online platforms, and so forth.

As shown in **Figure 1**, in the case of Hungarian, most municipalities achieve only the first level of bilingualism, as 83% of municipalities display bilingual signs, As for the other dimensions only a minority of municipalities implement all dimensions of the law: 46% ensuring oral communication, 22% communicate bilingually in writing, 22% translate official documents and a mere 6% provide bilingual forms to the public. In the case of municipalities, where Hungarians are in a majority in the local council, the situation is only slightly better, 94% of Hungarian-led municipalities display bilingual signs, 72% ensure oral communication, 35% communicate bilingually in writing, 32% translate official documents, and merely 8% provide bilingual forms to the public. In other words, these municipalities achieve bilingualism in oral communication as well, however, this is practically explained by the fact that in these towns, due to the high number of Hungarians, municipal staff are mostly Hungarian.

Figure 12. Hungarian language use in Romanian municipalities by the dimensions of administrative language use (N = 323)

Overall, the data paints a discouraging picture of the state of Hungarian language use, which has experienced a significant regression over the past 15 years. This decline can be attributed, on one hand, to the disappearance of NGOs that previously monitored and advocated for compliance with linguistic rights. On the other hand, with the absence of these independent actors, the Democratic Alliance of Hungarians in Romania (DAHR) has largely deprioritized this issue. Although the party established its own PONGO for advocacy services, its primary objective appears to be monopolizing the advocacy space rather than genuinely holding Hungarian-led municipalities accountable for their compliance with language rights.

1.4. Conclusions

The empirical research from 2023 demonstrates a distressing and systemic regression in the application of administrative minority language rights in Romania over the last fifteen years. Although the adoption of the 2019 Administrative Code (GEO no. 57/2019) legally consolidated and partially

expanded these rights, establishing clear obligations for bilingual forms, public notifications, and topographical signs in municipalities where a minority exceeds the 20% threshold, de facto implementation remains highly deficient and, in several aspects, is deteriorating.

The findings reveal a clear hierarchy of implementation, showing a sharp drop-off as soon as language rights move from purely symbolic gestures to functional administrative duties. Symbolic bilingualism remains relatively high, with 83% of municipal offices displaying bilingual facade signs, but actual administrative engagement in the minority language is severely restricted.

There is a visible trend toward the "informalization" of the Hungarian language. While half of the surveyed municipalities use Hungarian for informal communication on social media (Facebook), official, binding communication has degraded. Since 2014, the proportion of exclusively Romanian-language municipal websites has risen from 43% to 52%, a regression driven heavily by Hungarian-led administrations.

Despite clear legal provisions in the matter, the translation of crucial public documents has collapsed. Compliance with translating public interest notices, council meeting agendas, and council resolutions has decreased by more than half since 2008. Furthermore, despite the 2019 Administrative Code legally mandating the provision of bilingual administrative forms, only a negligible 5% of all eligible municipalities (and a mere 8% of Hungarian-led councils) comply.

Deconcentrated state entities, specifically national post offices and local police forces, operate almost entirely in Romanian. Police stations demonstrate a severe resistance to bilingualism, with bilingual facade signage dropping to 10% and oral communication in Hungarian standing at 14%, regardless of whether the municipality has a Hungarian political majority.

General regression is aggravated by a lack of political accountability. The disappearance of independent civil society monitoring groups has left a vacuum. The dominant minority political actor, the DAHR, has failed to hold its own elected local officials accountable, leading to a widespread deprioritization of the implementation of language rights within Hungarian-majority municipalities.

Ultimately, by failing to enforce the provisions of the Administrative Codex, the Romanian state is in systemic violation of its commitments under Articles 10 and 11 of the Framework Convention, relegating the Hungarian language to an informal, oral-only status and depriving minority citizens of their right to interact formally with public authorities in their mother tongue.

1.5. Recommendations

To ensure full compliance with Articles 10 and 11 of the Framework Convention and the domestic provisions of the 2019 Administrative Code, the Advisory Committee should recommend that Romania:

5.1. Establish oversight and accountability mechanisms

- Empower and allocate budgetary support for the National Council for Combating Discrimination (NCCD) in collaboration with the Romanian Institute for Research on National Minorities to systematically audit local public administrations, deconcentrated services, and police stations for compliance with the Administrative Code.
- Legislate clear administrative and financial penalties for municipal authorities and public institutions that fail to comply with mandatory bilingual obligations, such as the provision of bilingual forms and the translation of council resolutions.

5.2. Ensure the institutionalization and digitalization of written communication

- Enforce the requirement that all municipal websites in units exceeding the 20% threshold must be fully bilingual. Standardized, bilingual public-administration web templates should be developed and distributed by the central government to facilitate compliance.
- Use the bilingual forms catalog developed by the Romanian Institute for Research on National Minorities to eliminate local-level administrative holdups.

5.3. Address linguistic gaps in decentralized public services

- Implement affirmative action policies and targeted hiring quotas to recruit Hungarian-speaking staff for local councils, the police departments and post offices in minority-populated areas.
- Mandate the immediate installation of bilingual signage at all local police stations and public security facilities within municipalities meeting the 20% threshold, irrespective of local political leadership.

5.4. Promote proactive language use and technological solutions

- Provide technical and financial support for municipal administrations to implement bilingual automated telephone menus, encouraging citizens to use their preferred language from the onset of contact.
- Provide state-funded support to independent, non-governmental organizations to monitor and report on linguistic rights, ensuring that advocacy and compliance tracking are not monopolized by political parties.

3. Effective participation of Hungarians in decision-making (FCNM Article 15)

Article 15 requires governments to create the possibility for national minorities to effectively participate in cultural, social and economic life, and in public affairs. As Tove Malloy points out in an analysis on Article 15, “the right to participation in public affairs is often established through domestic legislation on national minorities”, while “such legislation complies with the principles of the FCNM, including equal opportunities and the right to self-definition as well as pluralism, both within minorities, and between organizations representing them.”⁴ In other words, effective participation of minorities in public affairs, would involve not only institutional solutions for minorities to participate in the decision-making, but it requires that minority participation be both democratic and transparent.

The Explanatory Report of the FCNM enumerates several forms of participation: 1) consultation with the members of the minorities, 2) involving minorities in the preparation and implementation process of legislation that would affect minorities directly, 3) effective involvement of persons belonging to national minorities in the decision-making process, 4) decentralized or local forms of government.

Romania does not have framework legislation to regulate minority participation, nor that it offers possibilities for minorities to organize decentralized or local forms of government, however it offers other types of possibilities for involvement and control over the decision-making and administrative process, from the participation at election, through ethnic parties to involvement in the preparation and implementation process, to consultation.

In the following we will present two cases of participation, which, although it expands the control of minority organizations over the minority institutional framework and public policy processes, simultaneously constitutes a severe violation of the principles of democracy and transparency.

2.1. Veto rights in appointing minority institution leaders

The Romanian Education Law provides minority communities with limited but essential control over their educational institutions through guaranteed representation in school leadership. Law no. 198/2023 on education establishes clear linguistic and representational requirements for school directors. In those schools where minority language education exists, one of the directors must belong to the minority community, and it is legally required to be fluent in the Hungarian language⁵ (Articles 59(7) and 195(1)). Furthermore, according to Article 195(1) in these cases, the appointment of the director is made in consultation with the organization representing the respective minority in the Romanian Parliament, or, if the minority lacks parliamentary representation, in consultation with the Parliamentary Group of National Minorities. In technical terms this means that candidates need to provide proof of language proficiency in the minority language (Article 3(6) of Ministerial Order no. 5080/2016) and a written document attesting to the consultation of the organization that represents

⁴ Tove H. Malloy: Commentary of Article 15 of the Framework Convention for the Protection of National Minorities. Rainer Hofmann, Tove H. Malloy, Detlev Rein (eds.): *The Framework Convention for the Protection of National Minorities. A Commentary*. Leiden – Boston: Brill Nijhoff, 2018. p. 278

⁵ This is not a novelty, as it was already present in Law no. 1/2011 on national education.

the respective minority in the Romanian Parliament, or a document attesting to the consultation of the Parliamentary Group of National Minorities (Article 3(7) of Ministerial Order no. 5080/2016).

As each minority is represented by a single ethnic organization, without realistic possibility for change or democratic pluralism, this consultation right essentially functions as a political veto or a requirement for political endorsement from a single party, rather than a genuine, transparent, and democratic community consultation. It reduces the selection of school directors to a process dependent on the approval of a specific political entity.

A worrying novelty is that the Democratic Alliance of Hungarians in Romania (DAHR) tries to further widen this type of control, as it plans to include a similar provision in the new Law on Cultural Management. According Article 3(4) of the draft released for public consultation,⁶ for public cultural institutions operating entirely or partially in the language of a national community, candidates have the obligation to submit a ***favorable opinion*** (*aviz favorabil*) to their application file from the organization representing that community in the Romanian Parliament, or from the Parliamentary Group of National Minorities, if it does not have parliamentary representation.

Requiring a favorable opinion (*aviz favorabil*) would grant a single political party a hard veto over the appointment of cultural institution directors, dropping all pretense of objective, professional, and transparent public competitions, converting the leadership of cultural institutions into political appointments completely controlled by the ethnic party. Furthermore, it is proof of escalating monopolization of power sought by DAHR, as compared to the provisions of the Law on education, it would transform the dominant minority political party from a consultative body into a gatekeeper.

2.2. Political control of funds provided through open calls for minority organizations

The Department for Interethnic Relations (DIR) is one of the most critical state bodies tasked with implementing minority rights. It is designed as an institution for minority representation, because historically, its leaders, a State Secretary and an Under-Secretary of State, are delegated by minority organizations. Until 2023, the Department was led by Enikő Katalin Laczikó (delegated by the Democratic Alliance of Hungarians in Romania – DAHR), who currently serves as an adviser at the Court of Accounts. The Department is currently led by Dincer Geafer, a member of the Turkish minority and former general secretary of the Democratic Union of Turkish-Muslim Tatars of Romania.

As the government's dedicated agency for minority policy, the DIR is responsible for distributing minority funding, enforcing anti-discrimination measures, and reporting on Romania's progress to the international community. A key activity of the DIR, also highlighted in Annex 2 of the State Report, is financing interethnic projects. These non-reimbursable funds aim to promote the cultural, linguistic, and religious identity of national minorities, safeguard their rights, and combat intolerance through annual open calls for cultural projects.⁷

While supporting identity-preserving and interethnic initiatives aligns directly with Article 5 of the Framework Convention, especially given the severe financial struggles faced by minority NGOs, the practical operation of this funding system raises serious concerns. Feedback from civil society and an

⁶ The proposal can be accessed on the webpage of the Ministry of Culture: <https://www.cultura.ro/proiect-de-lege-16/>

⁷ <https://dri.gov.ro/ro/ghid-de-finantare/>

analysis of the DIR's official website reveal two systemic flaws: a lack of transparency and apparent political bias.

First, the evaluation and selection process is highly opaque. Rejected organizations receive no professional feedback or justification for the decisions. Furthermore, the DIR fails to publish basic evaluation data online. There is no public record of the total number of submitted projects, and, with the sole exception of 2022, the evaluation scores and detailed results of the application process remain inaccessible to the public.

Second, there are serious concerns regarding political favoritism in fund distribution. A significant portion of the supported organizations are directly affiliated with DAHR. As illustrated in **Table 3** in the Annex, during the 2015–2023 period (when DIR was led by a DAHR representative), 20 Hungarian organizations received recurrent funding, meaning they were selected in at least four different years. Of these, nine are directly linked to the DAHR. These include:

- **Communitas Foundation** (established and controlled by the DAHR);
- **Transylvania Trust Foundation** (led by Csilla Hegedüs, former Minister of Culture on behalf of the DAHR/RMDSZ);
- **Identitás Foundation** (founded and directly controlled by the local DAHR branch in Satu Mare);
- **Csorgó Association** in Cârța/Karcsfalva (the birthplace of Hunor Kelemen, president of the DAHR, and controlled by local DAHR leaders);
- **Téka Foundation** in Gherla/Szamosújvár (a long-time strategic partner of the DAHR);
- **Mini JazzFestival Association** and **Cultura Nostra Association** in Miercurea Ciuc/Csíkszereda (which organize jazz and early music festivals in collaboration with the DAHR-led local council).

The assumption of political control is further supported by the fact that many of these organizations ceased to receive funding after 2023, following the change in the leadership of DIR. Consequently, there is a strong presumption within civil society that an organization's political relationship with the DAHR is the decisive factor in securing funding, rather than the professional merit of the application.

A similar trend toward the politicization of public funds can be observed within the Administration of the National Cultural Fund (AFCN). The primary decision-making body of the AFCN is its Council. By law, two members are appointed by the Ministry of Culture, one by the Romanian Cultural Institute, one by the Council of National Minorities (CMN), and seven by cultural NGOs.

In 2026, the Ministry of Culture restructured the AFCN Council (via Ministry Order no. 2561/2026) and appointed new members. Among the new appointees, the member representing the Council of National Minorities (Angéla Ferencz, director of the Harghita County Cultural Center) and one of the members representing cultural NGOs (Zsolt Karácsonyi, the DAHR Executive Vice-President for Culture) are directly linked to the DAHR.⁸ As the AFCN Council is responsible for establishing funding strategies, budgets, thematic priority areas, and appointing the evaluation committees, these appointments raise a serious risk that AFCN grants will become politicized, particularly from the perspective of the Hungarian minority, mirroring the issues observed within DIR.

⁸ <https://www.afcn.ro/afcn/consiliul-afcn.html>

3.3. Conclusion

In conclusion, while Romania's institutional framework seemingly provides avenues for national minorities to participate in public affairs, the practical implementation of these mechanisms severely undermines the principles of democracy, pluralism, and transparency central to Article 15 of the Framework Convention. Rather than empowering the Hungarian community, the current system has facilitated a monopolization of power by a single political actor, the Democratic Alliance of Hungarians in Romania. This is manifested in two parallel, alarming trends: first, the transformation of mandatory consultative processes into political vetoes over the leadership of educational institutions, and second, the systemic politicization of public funds through DIR, where financial support often correlates with political allegiance rather than professional merit. To ensure that minority rights are protected in a non-discriminatory and democratic manner, the Romanian government must shift from a system of political patronage to one of objective, transparent, and pluralistic governance.

3.4. Recommendations

To align state practices with the obligations set forth in Articles 5 and 15 of the Framework Convention, the Advisory Committee should recommend that Romania:

1. Ensure democratic pluralism and merit-based appointments

- Amend Article 195(1) of the Education Law (Law no. 198/2023) and reject similar provisions in the draft Law on Cultural Management to ensure that the appointment of school and cultural directors is not based on endorsement or "favorable opinions" (avize favorabile) from a single dominant political party.
- Establish structured, open, and multi-stakeholder consultation mechanisms with minority civil society that bypass political monopolies, ensuring that independent NGOs, academic institutions, and diverse community representatives are actively involved in decision-making processes.

2. Guarantee transparency and integrity in public funding

- Mandate that the Department for Interethnic Relations (DIR) publish all evaluation data on its official website, including the total number of submitted projects, final evaluation scores, and detailed, professional justifications for rejected applications.
- Restructure the project evaluation and selection committees within DIR to ensure they are composed of independent, non-partisan experts. Strict conflict-of-interest regulations must be enforced to prevent active political party executives from influencing public grant distribution.
- Review the appointment procedures under Ministry Order no. 2561/2026 to ensure that the civil society and minority representatives designated to the AFCN Council are politically independent and represent the authentic, pluralistic diversity of the cultural sector.

4. Regression in social security rights and structural discrimination: the proposed conditional child allowance reform (FCNM Article 4 and 12)

On April 29, 2026, the Democratic Alliance of Hungarians in Romania (DAHR) formally introduced a legislative proposal to the Senate⁹ to amend Law no. 61/1993 on child allowances and Law no. 198/2023 on public education.

The draft bill introduces three main modifications:

1. The restructuring of the universal state child allowance (*alocație pentru copii*) for school-aged children, making it conditional upon school attendance and behavior.
2. The extension of the monthly childcare allowance of 719 RON (granted for children aged 0–2) up to the age of 3.
3. The extension of the social scholarship system to preschool children.

The most alarming aspect of this proposal is the first provision. For children aged 3 to 18, the amendment proposes to slash the guaranteed universal child allowance by over 65%, reducing it from 292 RON to a mere 100 RON. The remaining 192 RON (bolstered by additional funds to reach 250 RON) would be redistributed as a conditional “Attendance scholarship” (*bursă de prezență*). To qualify for this scholarship, a child must: 1) maintain daily attendance in a preschool or school (excluding medically excused absences), and 2) achieve a perfect behavior grade (*Nota 10 la purtare*) in the preceding school year.

According to the authors’ explanatory memorandum, this “Attendance scholarship” aims to curb early school leaving. In their conception the bill aligns with European Union priorities to reduce dropout rates by establishing a legal mechanism that incentivizes continuous participation, reduces marginalization, and fosters labor market integration.

However, a critical human rights assessment reveals that this punitive, conditional scheme violates domestic constitutional law, international treaties, and the FCNM. If enacted, it would codify structural discrimination, disproportionately penalizing the most vulnerable, particularly Hungarian-speaking Roma children.

3.1. Human Rights and Legal Incompatibility

3.1.1. Violation of the Principle of Universality and Constitutional Precedent

In its Decision No. 2006/277, the Romanian Constitutional Court (CCR) ruled that conditioning the distribution of the state child allowance is unconstitutional. The Court based its reasoning on Article 49(2) of the Romanian Constitution, which mandates that “*the State shall grant state allowances for children and benefits for the care of sick or disabled children.*”

The CCR established that the child allowance is an **absolute, unconditional right** inherent to the status of being a child, entirely independent of school enrollment. Recognizing this constitutional barrier, the formulators of the 2026 bill attempted a procedural bypass. Rather than eliminating the universal allowance outright, they reduced the guaranteed portion to 40% (100 RON) and repackaged the rest

⁹ <https://www.senat.ro/Legis/Lista.aspx?cod=27698&pos=0&NR=b262&AN=2026>

as a conditional scholarship. While this maneuvering seeks to technically circumvent the unconstitutionality ruling, it violates the spirit of the Constitution. By stripping away 65% of the guaranteed universal allowance, the state would severely weaken its constitutional obligation to safeguard children's basic welfare.

3.1.2. Incompatibility with the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC)

While the proposal claims to enforce the right to education (Article 28, UNCRC) through attendance requirements, the mechanism directly violates Articles 26 and 27 of the same Convention:

- According to Article 26 *“every child has the right to benefit from social security, including social assistance.”* Basic social benefits designed to guarantee survival and basic well-being must not be conditioned on behavior or performance.
- According to Article 27 every child has the right to *“a standard of living adequate for their physical, mental, spiritual, moral and social development.”* While parents bear primary responsibility, the State is obligated to assist them through *“support programs, particularly regarding nutrition, clothing, and housing.”*

Reducing the universal allowance to 100 RON severely undermines these provisions. The “Attendance scholarship” punishes the child for systemic failures or parental hardships. If a child cannot attend school, the state responds by plunging their family deeper into poverty, directly threatening the child's access to food, adequate clothing, and stable housing.

Furthermore, the European Commission's *A whole-school approach to preventing early school leaving: Key policy messages* document¹⁰ explicitly warns against punitive assistance schemes. Instead of financial penalties, European standards recommend collaborative, non-punitive support structures, including inclusive curricula, early warning systems, targeted personal counseling, and active engagement with parents.

3.2. Structural discrimination and the targeting of vulnerable communities

Structural discrimination occurs when seemingly neutral administrative rules have a disproportionately hostile impact on specific, vulnerable groups who are prevented from complying due to systemic barriers. The legislative changes proposed by DAHR embody this dynamic.

3.2.1. The socio-economic realities of absenteeism

Extensive sociological research shows that chronic school absenteeism and early school leaving are not matters of individual "bad behavior" or parental apathy. Rather, they are symptoms of deep structural, regional, and infrastructural inequalities:

- Children in deep poverty frequently miss school because they lack winter shoes, adequate clothing, or basic nutrition. In some cases, they must perform seasonal labor to help their families survive.
- In rural and isolated areas, children frequently miss school during harsh weather due to a complete lack of school-busing networks or impassable roads.

¹⁰ https://education.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document-library-docs/early-school-leaving-group2015-policy-messages_en.pdf

- Wealthier urban families can afford private therapies and educational support to keep children with special educational need in school. Low-income rural families have no such access, leaving these children highly vulnerable to exclusion and subsequent absenteeism.

Cutting child allowance for these families deprives them of the very resources required to send their children to school in the first place. Conversely, middle-class urban children living in well-resourced environments will secure the “Attendance scholarship” effortlessly. This mechanism constitutes indirect, state-sanctioned discrimination.

3.2.2. The Punitive Use of Behavior Grades

Conditioning the scholarship on achieving a perfect behavior grade in the previous academic year is deeply flawed. Traumatized children, those from extremely marginalized backgrounds, and students with undiagnosed neurodivergent or special educational needs often struggle with rigid school environments.

Underfunded schools frequently use behavior grades as a disciplinary tool of first resort rather than offering psychological counseling or social support. Under the proposed law, the school system would weaponize its own institutional biases and pedagogical shortcomings to financially penalize the most vulnerable families.

3.2.3. Specific impact on the Hungarian-speaking Roma minority

While drafted in ethnically neutral terms, this legislation would have an immediate, devastating impact on the Hungarian-speaking Roma minority in Transylvania.

As documented in Chapter 2 of this report, 55.2% of all Hungarian-medium Roma students study in highly segregated, underfunded, Roma-majority educational sites. These schools suffer from severe infrastructure deficits, lack of counseling services, and high teacher turnover. Consequently, these segregated environments exhibit the highest dropout rates and lowest academic achievements.

By proposing these cuts amidst an ongoing cost-of-living crisis – and following consecutive government austerity measures targeting low-income groups – this bill effectively forces vulnerable groups to “compete” for basic survival funds. Because Hungarian-speaking Roma families face the highest rates of deep poverty, geographic isolation, and administrative exclusion (such as the denial of permanent identity documents documented in our Miercurea Ciuc case study), they will be the primary victims of these financial penalties.

Instead of addressing the root causes of segregation and systemic underfunding, this bill shifts the entire burden of state failure onto the shoulders of families in general, and marginalized Roma children in particular, trapping them in a permanent cycle of economic deprivation and educational exclusion.

3.3. Conclusions

The proposed amendment to Law no. 1993/61 and Law no. 2023/198, initiated by DAHR, represents a retrogressive step in social security and child protection, in violation of Articles 4 and 12 of the FCNM, the Romanian Constitution, and the UNCRC.

By conditioning 65% of the universal child allowance on school attendance and behavior grades, the bill establishes a system of structural and indirect discrimination. It punishes children for infrastructural, geographical, and socio-economic barriers that are the responsibility of the state.

The bill disproportionately harms the Hungarian-speaking Roma minority, who already experience systemic educational segregation, thereby aggravating existing ethnic inequalities and deep-seated social exclusion.

3.4. Recommendations

- Reject punitive social assistance models and ensure that the state child allowance (alocație) remains a strictly universal, unconditional, and un-reducible right of every child, in full compliance with Article 49 of the Romanian Constitution and Article 26 and 27 of the UNCRC.
- Align school dropout prevention strategies with European standards by investing in non-punitive, supportive structures. These must include at least the following:
 - Expanding the "Warm Meal" (Masă Caldă) program to all segregated and rural schools.
 - Ensuring free, reliable school transportation for all rural and marginalized areas.
 - Increasing the number of school counselors, psychologists, and mediators, particularly in Hungarian-medium and Roma-majority schools.

5. Annexes

Table 2. Municipalities with Hungarian population falling below the 20 percent threshold after 1992

Romanian name		County	Number of Hungarians in 2011	1992	2021
Fărău	Rural	Alba	151	26.5	12.7
Noșlac	Rural	Alba	191	20.7	13.0
Rădeși	Rural	Alba	171	24.0	15.3
Bucerdea Grânoasă	Rural	Alba	365	30.2	17.9
Chișineu Criș	Urban	Arad	1,306	23.1	19.7
Vinga	Rural	Arad	823	28.3	15.2
Aleșd	Rural	Bihor	1,105	22.2	12.4
Balc	Rural	Bihor	504	24.2	18.1
Ghirișu de Criș	Rural	Bihor	441	26.8	13.3
Oșorhei	Rural	Bihor	1,082	23.7	13.4
Tileagd	Rural	Bihor	1,017	26.8	19.3
Vadu Criéului	Rural	Bihor	671	20.1	18.5
Nuéeni	Rural	Bistrita-Nasaud	495	28.8	18.3
Petru Rareș	Rural	Bistrita-Nasaud	419	24.7	13.4
Uriu	Rural	Bistrita-Nasaud	585	27.4	18.3
Rupea	Urban	Brasov	706	22.6	16.1
Săcele	Urban	Brasov	4,499	27.2	18.1
Budila	Rural	Brasov	463	27.9	10.2
Cața	Rural	Brasov	483	32.4	19.8
Șercaia	Rural	Brasov	130	20.3	5.0
Târlungeni	Rural	Brasov	2,082	40.6	19.4
Teliu	Rural	Brasov	626	30.6	14.6
Crizbav	Rural	Brasov	282	30.1	10.5
Cluj Napoca	Urban	Cluj	33,603	22.8	13.9
Mca	Rural	Cluj	654	32.3	19.8
Mihai Viteazu	Rural	Cluj	1,013	32.6	19.4
Cătina	Rural	Cluj	255	21.5	17.0
Chinteni	Rural	Cluj	583	20.6	14.0
Cojocna	Rural	Cluj	567	21.1	15.3
Florești	Rural	Cluj	4,714	33.2	11.0
Geaca	Rural	Cluj	159	20.8	12.5
Viișoara	Rural	Cluj	931	25.5	17.6
Hăghig	Rural	Covasna	443	38.8	19.7
Vâlcele	Rural	Covasna	281	21.4	5.3
Toplița	Urban	Harghita	2,092	29.3	19.2
Sârmaș	Rural	Harghita	474	22.1	15.0
Baia Sprie	Oraș	Maramures	1,672	23.0	14.2
Albești	Rural	Mures	849	23.8	17.1
Batoș	Rural	Mures	546	21.0	14.8
Coroisânmartin	Rural	Mures	242	26.2	19.9
Nadeș	Rural	Mures	420	20.8	15.2

Ogra	Rural	Mures	387	30.7	17.6
Sârmaşu	Rural	Mures	1,097	27.5	19.0
Vânători	Rural	Mures	648	27.6	16.7
Botiz	Rural	Satu Mare	490	37.1	14.6
Şimleul Silvaniei	Oraş	Salaj	2,167	27.7	18.4
Cuplăplac	Rural	Salaj	212	20.2	14.3
Fildu de Jos	Rural	Salaj	194	21.9	16.5
Dumbraviţa	Rural	Timis	912	53.5	5.9
Dumbrava	Rural	Timis	417	22.0	17.6
Foieni	Rural	Timis	166	22.5	12.1
Giera	Rural	Timis	144	24.7	14.6
			74,929		

* compared to total population; ** compared to those who declared ethnicity

Source: 1992 and 2011 census results

Table 3. List of organizations, which received recurrent funds from DIR in the 2015–2023 period

Organization	Funded years (2015–2023)	Years	Affiliation to DAHR
Asociația Grupul Minimum Party	2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023	9	
Asociația Filmtett	2015, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023,	8	
Fundația Communitas	2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2022, 2023	8	an organization founded and controlled by DAHR
Asociația Culturală Szint Kulturális Egyesület	2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2021, 2022, 2023	7	
Asociația de Dans Popular al Maghiarilor din România	2015, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2023,	7	
Asociația Teatrală Shoshin	2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021,	7	
Asociația Bolyongó Színházi Egyesület	2017, 2018, 2019, 2021, 2022, 2023,	6	
Asociația Culturală și de Tineret din Văcărești	2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2021, 2022,	6	an organization functioning in Văcărești/Csíkvacársárcs, controlled by DAHR
Asociația Grupul Pont	2015 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020	6	
Fundația Culturală Teka	2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2022, 2023,	6	an organization functioning in Gherla/Szamosújvár, a long time strategic partner of DAHR
Fundația Transilvania Trust	2015, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2021, 2022,	6	lead by Csilla Hegedüs, former Ministry of Culture on behalf of RMDSZ
Uniunea Democratică a Tineretului Maghiar Jud. Mureș - UDTM	2015, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021,	6	youth organization functioning in Târgu Mureș/Marosvásárhely
Asociația Csorgo	2017, 2018, 2019, 2021, 2022,	5	an organization in Cârța/Karcfalva the birthplace of Hunor Kelemen, president of DAHR, controlled by local DAHR leaders
Asociația Yuppi Camp	2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2021,	5	
Asociația Castel Teleki - Teleki Kastely	2015, 2016, 2017, 2018,	4	
Asociația Media Index	2015, 2016, 2017, 2021,	4	cultural and non-profit organization based in Cluj-Napoca, founded and is led by individuals closely affiliated with RMDSZ
Asociația Mini JazzFestival	2015, 2016, 2017, 2018,	4	organizes the Csíki Jazz Festival in partnership with the Harghita County Cultural Center, local council of Miercurea Ciuc/Csíkszereda and the council of Harghita County
Asociația Puppet Media - Media Marionette	2018, 2019, 2020, 2022,	4	
Fundația Identitas Alapítvány	2017, 2019, 2020, 2021	4	an organization founded and controlled directly by the local RMDSZ branch in Satu Mare
Asociația Cultura Nostra Egyesület	2015, 2016, 2017, 2018	4	organizes the Miercurea Ciuc Early Music Festival in partnership with the Harghita County Cultural Center